

Lusitanian pedoclimatic region

Location

Spain (Galicia – A Limia, Xinzo)

Key Issues

- » High incidence of **cyst nematodes, common scab, and fungal diseases** in potato crops.
- » **Reduced yields** and profitability due to pest-related crop devaluation.
- » **Low soil pH** management **limits phosphorus availability**, increasing reliance on **synthetic fertilizers**.
- » Routine use of pesticides and heavy machinery leads to **biodiversity loss, soil compaction, and pollution**.
- » **Long-term degradation of soil ecosystem services**.

SoildiverAgro Approach

Five strategies tested:

- » **Diversified rotations** with legume inclusion.
- » Use of *Solanum sisymbriifolium* as a trap crop.
- » Application of **mycorrhizal fungi**.
- » **Reduced phosphorus fertilization**.
- » Implementation of a **pest alert system**.
- » **Main objective:** Reduce external inputs and enhance **soil biodiversity, productivity, and long-term sustainability**.

Benefits

- » **Trap crops** reduce **nematodes** and **pesticide** use.
- » **Legumes** fix **nitrogen** and enrich soil.
- » **Mycorrhizae** boost **fertility** and **soil structure**.
- » **Precision agriculture** cuts **costs** and reduces **pollution**.
- » **Pest alert systems** support **sustainability** with CAP-backed resilience.

Within the **Lusitanian pedoclimatic** region, the case studies conducted as part of the SoildiverAgro Project focused on the A Limia region (Province of Ourense, Autonomous Community of Galicia, Spain), an area characterized by intensive agricultural activity in which potatoes are the primary crop, traditionally rotated with wheat.

This region is currently facing significant agricultural challenges, including a **high incidence of cyst nematodes, common scab in potato crops, and various fungal diseases**, resulting in reduced agricultural yields. Furthermore, due to the prevalence of these pests and diseases, potatoes are frequently devalued in the market, leading to decreased profitability.

Another challenge lies in the current strategy used to manage common scab, which involves maintaining soil pH below 5. While this approach can suppress the pathogen, it also reduces phosphorus availability, thereby prompting the use of external phosphorus fertilization. As a result, **large quantities of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides are routinely applied**. Although this intensive input application can temporarily increase productivity, it also raises production costs and has led to a decline in both aboveground and belowground biodiversity, increased soil and water pollution, and greater soil compaction due to the frequent use of heavy machinery for pesticide application. These effects collectively degrade soil ecosystem services and reduce the long-term sustainability of agriculture in the region.

Given these major challenges, several sustainable agricultural strategies have been tested in this area, including: a) **diversification of crop rotations**, including the introduction of leguminous crops;

b) **use of a trap crop** to naturally eliminate nematode cysts; c) **application of mycorrhizal fungi**; d) **reduction in phosphorus fertilization**; and d) **implementation of a pest alert system**.

The main objectives of these practices were to reduce the use of pesticides and external fertilizers, while increasing soil biodiversity and maintaining—or even improving—agricultural yields. In addition, the reduction in external inputs is expected to lower production costs, thereby increasing farmers' profits and reducing soil and water pollution. Improved soil biodiversity is also expected to enhance overall soil health and fertility in the medium–long term, contributing to the resilience and sustainability of agricultural systems.

Results

Based on the results obtained in this project, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

- Promote the use of *Solanum sisymbriifolium* as a trap crop in potato fields** infested with cyst nematodes in the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region and assess its potential in other pedoclimatic regions. It is also recommended to **include subsidies for this trap crop** (*S. sisymbriifolium*) under the CAP, at least equivalent to those for wheat, as it has demonstrated very high effectiveness in eliminating nematode cysts. This helps reduce the need for synthetic nematicides and ensures sustainable potato production over time by preventing affected fields from being quarantined.
- Promote the inclusion of legume crops in crop rotations, reinforcing support for legume cultivation under the CAP.** The inclusion of legumes has proven effective in naturally fixing nitrogen, significantly reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers in potato cultivation. In addition to improving soil fertility, this practice has also enhanced soil biodiversity and other ecosystem services.

- Encourage the adoption of precision agriculture technologies** to reduce and optimize fertilizer use without negatively affecting crop yield or quality.
- Promote the use of mycorrhizal fungi in potato cultivation**, as it has been shown to increase soil fertility, improve soil structure, and enhance soil biodiversity.
- Support the implementation of pest alert systems** to reduce the number of chemical fungicide applications by addressing the trade-off between fungicide use and yield losses. Additionally, **it is strongly recommended to promote long-term research on this agricultural practice**, collecting data on crop yields, soil fertility, and other ecosystem services over extended periods and under varying climatic conditions. This will allow for a more accurate assessment of the agronomic and economic long-term benefits of implementing such systems, as short-term results did not prove to be economically viable compared to conventional practices (e.g., intensive and routine application of synthetic fungicides). It is also suggested to invest in enhancing these systems by incorporating aerobiological data, which would enable more precise predictions of disease outbreaks in the study area. Finally, **financial compensation through the CAP should be provided to farmers who adopt these pest alert systems to offset potential short-term losses**.

From the **SoildiverAgro** project perspective, the implementation of these policy recommendations would significantly enhance the competitiveness of the agricultural sector in this region, while also increasing the long-term resilience and sustainability of agricultural systems—primarily through improved biodiversity and enhanced soil ecosystem services.

Finally, it is important to emphasize that these measures would also contribute substantially to reducing soil and water pollution, thereby decreasing ecological and human health risks.

